

The role of statokinetic and hypoxic exercises in improving the accuracy of movements performed in sports games

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Abstract

This article examines the accuracy of execution and mechanisms for stabilizing standard technical actions performed in sports games, including penalty kicks in football and shooting in basketball, handball, and football, based on an analysis of scientific sources. The study provides a comparative analysis of published scientific-theoretical, educational-methodological, and practical research on this topic.

Additionally, the article discusses modern approaches to improving performance and maintaining stable standard movements over long periods - such as sensorimotor exercises, correction of technical movements through video analysis, targeted repetition regimens, psychophysiological monitoring, proprioceptive training, and methods of simulating game situations. The article is enriched with practical recommendations aimed at strengthening athletes' ability to perform movements with high accuracy in standard situations.

Keywords: sports games, standard movements, movement accuracy, motor stability, performance, penalty kicks, goal shooting, technical stabilization, neuromuscular control, sensorimotor training, biomechanics, proprioception, motor memory.

Introduction

In recent years, specialist coaches and researchers have been focusing less on increasing the volume and intensity of training or optimizing their ratio to further improve sports performance. Instead, they are emphasizing the search, identification, and practical implementation of stable work capacity, functional resources, and energy reserves that enable athletes to withstand and overcome the effects of intense loads applied during annual training stages, especially in competitive cycles. Most studies published in scientific sources in this field are aimed at examining the disruption of static and dynamic balance observed in sports with extremely variable directions and emergency situations. They investigate the occurrence of unstable states that negatively impact movement accuracy and effectiveness. These studies also focus on increasing the stability of such abilities through special non-traditional exercises.

For example, according to A.G.

Rodionova's findings, in sports practice, especially in sports games, the effectiveness of a movement depends on its execution at high speed, accurately, purposefully, and efficiently. Such abilities are associated with mastering new movements based on the athlete's repertoire of previously formed movements, differentiating the structural elements of movement (distinguishing the limits of muscle tension and time intervals, coordinating body parts in an appropriate sequence, etc.), and skillfully executing combinational movements with agility. However, it is acknowledged that for the effective performance of these movements, the athlete must have a well-developed ability to maintain static and dynamic balance. It is emphasized that the purposeful demonstration of these abilities and the precise execution and control of complex, particularly variable movements, depend on the integrated activity of nerve centers operating in the cerebral hemispheres, including various analyzers (visual, auditory, tactile, proprioceptive, vestibular).

Based on his research, V.I. Lyakh emphasizes that in situational sports with variable characteristics, the successful execution of various movements (technical and tactical techniques), especially combinations of movements (tactical combinations), depends on several factors. These include the ability to sense muscular activity (contraction, extension, tension, stretching, etc.), spatial-temporal coordination, balance maintenance, adaptation from one movement to another, and statokinetic stability. It is crucial to pay special attention to these factors both when teaching all movements and during their development.

R. T. Jackson conducted research on skilled football players and, based on the results obtained, concluded that regularly performing exercises with abruptly changing directions in emergency situations during training allows the receptors of the vestibular analyzer to adapt to such exercises, thus increasing balance stability. Nevertheless, it is acknowledged that

continuous training of balance stability can positively influence the execution of movements with even higher effectiveness.

Results and discussion

According to several authors, the stability of maintaining balance in a vertical position, both with and without visual control, in athletes, including football players, does not differ from the balance stability observed in non-athletes. It is possible that in simple tests, lower control centers are involved in regulating balance stability. However, in complex situations (conditions), body balance control becomes difficult and the difference in balance

vestibular analyzer in athletes through rotational movement exercises serves as a foundation for maintaining stability even during complex movements.

According to A. A. Zaitsev, V. F. Zaitseva, and A.E. Tarasov, in football (and other sports), intense movements performed in extreme situations along rapidly changing directions during gameplay can, firstly, trigger signs of fatigue, and secondly, such loads can directly affect the receptors of the vestibular analyzer. This not only causes imbalance but also impairs the ability to distinguish and control the coordination of decisive movements crucial in the game, as well as weakening the

Table 1. A complex of statokinetic and hypoxic exercises to improve the effectiveness of standard movements in qualified student athletes engaged in sports games

No.	Exercise name	Rules of execution	Duration	HR bpm	Recovery time
I. Statokinetic exercises					
1	Semi-squat position	Body upright, arms at sides	3×30 s	150-160	1 minute
2	One-legged ball pass	Hand forward, maintain balance	3×20 times	150-160	1 minute
3	Side jump and stop	2 s balance after jumping	4×8 times	155-165	1 minute
4	Quick start from static position	5 s sprint from static position	5×10 m	160-170	1 minute
5	Passing the ball while standing on tiptoes	Body straight, maintaining balance	3×30 s	150-160	1 minute
6	Initial position: standing on one leg from a bench	Maintain balance for 20 s	3×20 s	150-155	1 minute
7	Balance exercise with change of direction	Between special obstacles 3-5 m apart	4×8 times	155-165	1 minute
8	Dynamic squat + jump	Quickly lift legs while maintaining balance	4×10 times	160-165	1 minute
II. Hypoxic exercises					
9	Running while holding breath	20-30 m, holding breath	6-8 times	160-170	1.5 minutes
10	30 s fast running + 10 s holding breath	With intervals	4-5 times	170-180	1.5 minutes
11	Hypoxic squats	Performed while exhaling	3×20 times	165-175	1.5 minutes
12	Hypoxic game elements	Pass, through pass, shot	5 minutes	170-180	1.5 minutes
13	Running with the ball under hypoxic conditions	Hold breath, at maximum speed	4×15 m	170-180	1.5 minutes
14	Hypoxic rising exercise	Quickly stand up from sitting position while holding breath	3×12 times	165-170	1.5 minutes
15	Hypoxic turning exercise	Pass or dribble with a 90° turn	4×10 m	170-175	1.5 minutes
16	Hypoxic combination cycle	10 s fast run + 10 s squat-stand + 10 s passing	3×5 cycles	170-180	1.5 minutes

stability increases. Especially when rotational acceleration movements affect the vestibular analyzer, the stability of maintaining both static and dynamic balance may decrease. Therefore, the authors acknowledge that developing the

accuracy of both simple and complex motor reactions. In their opinion, non-specialized simple static or stabilographic tests are insufficient for an objective and qualitative assessment of balance stability in both athletes and non-athletes. In such cases (tests), the

control role of the vestibular analyzer in maintaining balance may be passive. However, when using these tests, if rotational movement loads that acutely affect the vestibular analyzer are applied, a decrease in balance stability is observed.

Studies conducted in this area have shown that high stability in maintaining balance during statokinetic movements, such as running in rapidly changing directions, turning, and rotational movements, allows football players to maintain coordination and accuracy in their technical and tactical actions. Therefore, when assessing the stability of maintaining such balance, researchers recommend using tests like holding the ball with the right foot, running around posts from both left and right sides, and performing the same test while dribbling the ball. The significance of the results obtained from these tests lies in the fact that the higher the stability of balance, the more effective the accuracy of passing or heading the ball, as well as directing it towards the goal, can be for football players.

According to another group of expert scientists, in sports practice, including sports games, the ability to maintain dynamic balance is of paramount importance in performing almost all simple and coordinatively complex movements, ensuring movement accuracy and effectiveness. This ability serves the biomechanics of movement - coordinating the centers of gravity of the body and body parts, and muscles in a hierarchical order corresponding to the purpose and structure of the performed movement, as well as ensuring the movement's effectiveness. They even emphasized that the ability to maintain dynamic balance creates the foundation for the effectiveness of technical-tactical actions and skill retention, enabling the demonstration of movement qualities (speed-strength, agility, endurance, flexibility, jumping ability) with "pure" and high efficiency.

Many scholars emphasize that the high or record-breaking sports results demonstrated in highly competitive sports competitions are not maintained for as long as they were in the past; on the contrary, they frequently improve and change. This is not directly related to the volume and intensity of training sessions or their ratio, possibly by reducing the former and increasing the latter. Indeed, today in high-performance sports, intense competitive processes are taking place at the limits of

maximum possibilities. It is known from sources that today, during sports training and competitions, increased attention is being paid to issues such as the intensification of local or global fatigue symptoms, their elimination, restoration and enhancement of functional organ activity related to work capacity, and the ability to maintain technical and tactical skills under the influence of intense loads. It is known that during intense training and long-duration competitions, oxygen deficiency (O_2) occurs in athletes' bodies, resulting in decreased work capacity. Not only does motor activity decline, but the coordination of "skill" is also disrupted, and performance is "lost".

Scientists recommend using hypoxic-hypercapnic (increased CO_2) exercises, "catching" breathing exercises, and relaxation or recreational exercises in athletes' daily routines (in the morning, before and after training sessions) to address such issues. For instance, O.S. Krasnikova, based on her research, acknowledges that in highly skilled athletes, breathing exercises through special respirator masks with short breaks lasting 5-8 minutes can increase the body's ability to function actively even under O_2 deficiency. However, for athletes with moderately developed work capacity, hypoxic exercises applied in such a regimen may result in a shorter and more effective recovery process. In athletes with below-average work capacity, both work capacity and adaptation to hypoxic conditions were observed to progress slowly.

According to M.L. Latash, conducting training sessions for athletes in conditions of exercising hypoxic stability at moderate mountain altitudes or on plains can lead to an increase in hemoglobin, a rise in blood oxygen levels, and an improvement in aerobic performance [80; 144-150]. G.P. Millet and R. Faiss state that one of the most effective methods for restoring athletes' functional capabilities, increasing their aerobic endurance, and enhancing physical performance is training in mountainous areas or performing hypoxic exercises on plains. They emphasize that regularly engaging in hypoxic exercises under simulated conditions (on plains) can create an effect similar to training on a mountain slope at an altitude of 4000-5000 m above sea level. The effectiveness of hypoxic-hyperoxic training based on interval periods depends on the athlete's actual functional state. For instance, in athletes with average physical work capacity,

such training results in faster recovery of football players' organ functions. However, if these training sessions are used with athletes whose physical work capacity is below average, the recovery process is observed to be less effective and may be accompanied by slight strain on heart activity. A.A. Artikov notes that in sports practice, it has become customary to conduct training sessions in mid-altitude mountain areas to enhance physical work capacity, restore and strengthen the capabilities of football players. However, while training in such conditions effectively develops hypoxic capabilities, it is acknowledged that this approach entails significant expenses. Therefore, according to his opinion, it is more practical to utilize hypoxic exercises based on the exogenous respiratory (external breathing) mechanism in natural conditions on flat terrain .

E.F. Myasnikova, E.V. Golovikhin, and T.B. Zorina, based on their research on basketball players, karate practitioners, and judokas, concluded that the use of hypoxic-hypercapnic (increase in O₂) exercises before and between training sessions in the pre-competition training cycle and during the competition period can help eliminate signs of fatigue that developed during basic training cycles, restore work capacity, and contribute to the stabilization of competition performance. A.A. Artikov and Sh.T. Shukurova also conducted research on football players using a similar approach, acknowledging that the combined use of hypoxic-hypercapnic exercises with training sessions not only serves as a basis for restoring and improving the physical and functional capabilities of football players but also helps maintain their technical and tactical skills during competitive cycles.

A.Ya. Stepanov, in collaboration with his co-authors, conducted research on the gradual increase of oxygen deficiency in a special pressure chamber (simulating conditions at altitudes of 1500 m, 2000 m, and 3500 m above sea level over 5 days). They concluded that hypoxic training under these conditions can effectively develop both static endurance and physical work capacity in athletes.

Conclusion

Comparative analysis of bibliographic data revealed that even leading athletes experience failures when executing standard penalty shots in sports games (such as penalties

in football, free throws in basketball, and penalty throws in handball). This problem is primarily associated with two factors. Firstly, the sharp changes in direction, sprints, and rotational movements performed during the game cause a state of imbalance, disrupting equilibrium and consequently negatively affecting the accuracy and effectiveness of penalty shots. Secondly, these movements, as a combination of aerobic and anaerobic loads, lead to an increase in oxygen debt in the athletes' bodies. Nevertheless, it can be acknowledged that the topic chosen for this dissertation is extremely relevant from both scientific-methodological and practical perspectives.

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